

Towards Bologna's Civic Twin: For an Environmental and Democratic Intelligence

PianetaLab Report, May 2026

<https://www.pianeta.org/pianetalab/>

September 2025 marked the launch of PianetaLab, an initiative designed to address environmental, social, and digital challenges starting from the local context, under the patronage of the Technical University of Munich (TUM) and the European Climate Pact. The aim is to create spaces for dialogue and co-design among citizens, institutions, and local actors, fostering discussion and participation. In Bologna, we engaged with the Digital Twin, managed by the Municipality of Bologna, with the goal of improving citizens' involvement in the development of this important tool for the future of urban life. The activities of PianetaLab in Bologna are part of a broader pathway promoted by the association Pianeta, which operates nationally on issues related to social inequalities and climate change. The central objective of the initiative in Bologna is to collectively reflect on the concept of the city's **digital civic twin**: understood not as a purely technical tool, but as a democratic and inclusive instrument capable of supporting and monitoring public policies and concretely improving people's lives.

In this document, we have collected the outcomes of conversations held with citizens of Bologna, both online and in person, with various actors from the scientific community, with local institutions, and especially through three public events held on 13 September 2025, 13 December 2025, and 13 February 2026. In preparing this document, we drew on academic studies on the use of digital twins, participation, and ethical data governance, conducted by the TUM Public Science Lab, the Ethical Data Initiative, and the Chair of Philosophy and History of Science and Technology.

Main challenges for the development and use of the digital twin

- **Translate the digital twin into concrete changes in everyday life**, particularly in the areas of mobility, safety, and health.
- **Develop accessible and inclusive ways to interact with the digital twin and understand its potential and limitations.**
- **Collect and use data responsibly in order to represent vulnerable communities** (children, older people, people with disabilities, disadvantaged families, migrants, etc.) and capture their needs.
- Invest in tools to **implement** what the digital twin identifies as necessary to improve citizens' quality of life.
- Use the digital twin to **overcome social fragmentation and create new synergies and collaborations** among institutions, services, industry, and communities.

Priorities for addressing these challenges

- **PARTICIPATION:** promote citizens' involvement in the development and use of the digital twin.
- **COMMUNICATION:** improve communication with citizens about the activities of the digital twin and opportunities for participation.
- **TRAINING:** encourage the use of the digital twin as a platform for the collaborative development of skills among all participants.
- **SERVICES:** connect public services with cutting-edge technologies.
- **DATA GOVERNANCE:** invest in methods to test the security, reliability, fairness, and functionality of data, as well as the ways in which computational models use them.
- **PUBLIC GOOD:** prioritize non-commercial infrastructures and services explicitly oriented toward the public interest.
- **TRANSPARENCY:** ensure that sensitive data are used for purposes of public interest and in a transparent manner.
- **SECURITY:** prevent misuse of the system while enabling citizens to intervene in cases of errors or omissions.
- **ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT:** reduce the environmental footprint of the digital twin.

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What is Bologna's Digital Twin?

- The urban digital twin consists of a series of digital models that collect and combine data on different aspects of the city, including mobility, climate, housing, schools, green spaces, and other urban features. It therefore makes it possible to identify trends, challenges, and potential solutions for life in Bologna.
- The Civic Twin project in Bologna is promoted and developed through a collaboration between the Municipality of Bologna, the National Research Centre for High Performance Computing, Big Data and Quantum Computing at the Tecnopolo, the University of Bologna, and the Kessler and Rusconi Chigi Foundations. Officially launched in 2022, following a long decade-long process of logistical, scientific, and administrative development, the Twin is currently under construction and is expected to become progressively operational over the next five years.
- This is therefore a valuable period for facilitating dialogue among scientists, public administrators, associations, companies, media, committees, and citizens, so that citizens' input becomes visible to the technical teams finalizing different parts of the Twin, and so that a relationship of trust and mutual exchange of information can be established between those promoting the Twin and those experiencing its implementation. For this reason, PianetaLab has proposed contributing to a process of dialogue and open communication about the existence and potential of the Twin, together with various associations and actors from the third sector operating in the province of Bologna. Our aim is to support the authorities responsible for the project and help citizens understand the importance of the Twin for their future lives, as well as identify effective ways to interact with this tool.
- One of the most important functions of the Twin is to simulate scenarios—for example, what happens to traffic or air quality if the climate changes, if mobility patterns are modified, or if a new building is constructed—and therefore to better understand how the city functions and how it can be improved.
- Many cities around the world are developing digital twins, with hundreds of projects currently underway. Bologna's Twin is one of the few with an explicitly civic mission: the project aims to maximize citizens' participation and the contribution of the Twin to the public good.

Why is it important?

- It is essential that the Twin is built on strong scientific foundations and reliable data, but also—and above all—on the feedback of Bologna's residents, who know their city better than anyone else and understand how they would like it to develop in the future.
- What does it mean to improve the city? In what ways does the city become more liveable, and for whom? There are many valid answers to these questions. Which ones will be prioritized by the Twin is a decision that must be made collectively, through greater public involvement, transparency in decision-making, and accessibility of information.
- It is also essential to think together about how the Twin will be used, how citizens can interact with these tools, and what options will exist to modify the system if it does not work properly.
- This means **collectively learning about the limits and possibilities of the Twin**. It is not a magic tool, but a mathematical model based on specific data. Having the ability

to understand which data are used by the system and how they are interpreted is crucial for developing effective ways to interact with the model, as well as for identifying which data are missing and how they can be collected and processed safely and responsibly with respect to citizens. For this reason, the Twin must be accompanied by **tools and activities aimed at educating users** and enabling a basic understanding of what the system can and cannot do.

- For the Twin to become not only a technical model but also a civic tool, **governance and participation must be placed at the centre**. Without this, policies risk being neither effective nor aligned with real needs. PianetaLab, in collaboration with the Municipality of Bologna and researchers, is contributing to a process designed to facilitate dialogue among different voices and interests, with the aim of achieving this goal.

Key challenges

The main challenges identified concern four fundamental needs:

- (1) The need to **use the digital twin to bring about concrete changes in everyday life**, with visible effects within the community.
- (2) The need to **develop accessible and inclusive ways of interacting with the twin**, so that users can understand its possibilities and limitations, contribute to its functioning, and report any problems.
- (3) The need to **collect and use data responsibly in order to represent vulnerable communities** and capture their needs.
- (4) The need to have funding not only to build the digital twin as a diagnostic and monitoring tool, but also to **implement** what it identifies as necessary to improve citizens' lives.

In particular, the following suggestions were made:

- Pay attention to sustainability — for example, how can we reduce the environmental impact of artificial intelligence tools used in sustainable mobility projects?
- Connect Bologna's transport systems and services (especially at the metropolitan level) with cutting-edge technologies.
- Develop or modify existing data collection systems with explicit attention to children, older people, people with disabilities, disadvantaged families, and migrants, investing in methods to test the security, reliability, fairness, and functionality of data, as well as the ways in which computational models use them.
- Improve communication with citizens about the activities of the digital twin and health prevention (for example through schools, community centres, hospitals, and educational and consultation activities).

The loss of children's autonomy was highlighted, along with **the importance of creating safe urban environments that support children's development and independent mobility**. In particular, the following suggestions were made:

- Improve the city's transport and **mobility** infrastructure.
- Implement systems that make the city **safer**, especially at night (for example, monitoring systems).

- Make **children** visible as citizens of the future by investing in educational activities and in data systems and modelling specifically dedicated to childhood.

The issue of **data quality and governance** also emerged, with attention to digital sovereignty and the ethical use of information, in order to ensure reliable models that are useful to citizens. In particular, the following suggestions were made:

- Use data that represent the population in a responsible and accurate way, and whose origin and provenance can be traced.
- Where possible, use, collect, store, and analyse data that are not dependent on commercial providers—especially those based outside the EU—while prioritising non-commercial infrastructures and services of a public or community nature.
- Ensure that sensitive data, including territorial data, are used for purposes of public interest, and that when they are used by private companies, this happens transparently.
- Enable citizens to correct inaccurate data or add relevant information. This raises the question: how can this be done in a way that remains open to the public while still being manageable by public administration and the digital twin itself? How can misuse of the system be prevented (including by artificial bots), while ensuring transparency regarding the data and analyses supported by the twin, and enabling productive interactions between citizens and the digital twin?

The greatest challenge concerns **citizen involvement**, particularly of the most vulnerable groups, those with lower levels of digital access, or those who are simply less covered by existing services, through transparency and clear communication aimed at encouraging participation. In particular, the following suggestions were made:

- Reflect on how a project such as the Twin can be **personalised** without turning it into a **surveillance tool**, and consider what role **consent** should play.
- Find solutions for how **citizens can interact** with the digital twin once it becomes operational. For example, how can they **submit complaints** or **integrate existing information**?
- **Involve citizens** in the construction of the technologies that affect them, for example by making use of **neighbourhood community centres**.
- Consider the needs of the most **vulnerable groups** when building the digital twin, making the city and public transport **accessible**—for example, to **wheelchair users, strollers, and children**. At the same time, use the digital twin to **bring discrimination to light** and give visibility to those affected by it.
- For example, it is essential to represent the “**real**” **Bologna** in the model, including people with **migrant backgrounds**. Their experiences, **linguistic and professional skills** are a strategic resource for the city and must find space in **data collection and service design**, overcoming linguistic and cultural barriers. In particular, the role of **migrant women entrepreneurs** is highlighted, as they make a significant contribution to the economy and **social regeneration**. The expertise of migrants in navigating **public services** is also emphasised, as well as the need to work with **migrant communities and related associations** to overcome the significant challenges of **integration into the social fabric**.
- Another important case concerns **non-binary identities**, which must be explicitly included in order to develop **effective policies**.

- Reflecting on children’s experiences in the city, it was emphasised that a more **“playable” and accessible city** is a city of **relationships**—safer and fairer for everyone. The Twin should therefore contribute to imagining **educational urban spaces** capable of promoting **autonomy, safety, and social interaction**, moving beyond an urban model designed almost exclusively around the **adult car driver**.
- The Twin could also support the coordination of **food production and distribution** by helping analyse how Bologna’s citizens eat, mapping neighbourhoods, school canteens, hospitals, and public facilities, and assessing the quality and origin of food. This approach could promote agroecological models, reduce healthcare costs in the long term, and support equitable access to healthy food by connecting urban, agricultural, and public health policies. The experience of markets in the Bologna Apennines—examples of virtuous connections between producers and consumers—illustrates how the Twin could help collect data on the health of mountain agriculture, support quality supply chains, and reflect on fairness in food distribution.
- The experience of those working with people recovering from comas and their families is particularly valuable, highlighting **disability as a result of the interaction between individuals and their environment**. The digital twin could help assess the impact of urban transformations—such as the tram system or the redevelopment of public spaces—on accessibility and quality of life, reducing the gap between action plans and their concrete implementation in the territory. Hospitals play a fundamental role as institutions of encounter and care, which could be strengthened through a dedicated use of the Twin.
- Finally, **territorial management needs are also crucial in order to better address present and future climate emergency challenges**. These include the use of green spaces to improve air quality and prevent landslides, the management of waterways especially in cases of flooding, and the coordination of public services and citizens’ actions during emergencies.

It is emphasized that there is a **need to start from concrete problems**—such as housing, population aging, the digital divide, flooding, and land-use management—in order to make the digital twin a useful and understandable tool. The example of elderly women living alone in Bologna (whose health and mobility could be explicitly highlighted as a project within the digital twin) shows how combining different data sources could help envision new models of housing and welfare. Applied to urgent situations, such as summer heat waves, the digital twin could support preventive policies and provide citizens with rapid and accessible responses. At the same time, the text stresses the importance of engaging with, contributing to, and learning from digital twin experiences in other Italian and international cities. It also highlights the need to coordinate Bologna’s digital twin with other digital services, such as regional and national digital twins dedicated to air quality monitoring and management.

Conclusions and Recommendations

- The digital twin should not become a technology that “governs from above,” as often happens with private digital platforms run by American companies such as Google or Meta. The digital twin is based on Italian and European technologies and experiences, and is funded primarily through public investment from the Italian government and the European Union. The hope is that **this tool will develop with and**

for the residents of Bologna (and the wider region), reflecting their needs and taking into account the everyday realities of the city and region.

- The digital twin **offers opportunities for education, training, and skills development** at many levels and across all sectors of society, both for citizens and for the public and private organizations that will use it. It is a technological platform that works best when it is integrated into everyday life through open and collaborative development.
- The challenge is twofold: **to make the digital twin understandable and accessible** without expecting citizens to suddenly become digital experts, while at the same time **enabling them to interact** with the tool, provide input, and contribute to decision-making processes.
- The digital twin is a complex and sensitive instrument to build for the scientists working on it, and difficult for public administrations to manage. For this reason, dialogue with citizens is necessary not only to gather feedback and requests, but also to **increase awareness of what the digital twin can and cannot do**—and therefore which uses may be beneficial in the future and which should be avoided.
- The usefulness of the digital twin is also emphasized as a means of **making institutional decision-making more transparent and understandable**, while facilitating dialogue with civic associations interested in collaborating on the development of the city.
- At the same time, concerns about sensitive data and the right to privacy are raised in relation to decisions about what kinds of data should be made accessible, to whom, and for what purposes. The analysis of open data must be accompanied by **safeguards that protect the rights and well-being of individuals and communities**. The digital twin should not become a “Big Brother” surveillance system, but rather a tool that fosters trust, participation, and shared responsibility. This requires a **data governance** framework that facilitates communication without exacerbating existing social vulnerabilities.
- The discussion also highlights the importance of **overcoming fragmentation among different institutions and digital platforms** by improving system interoperability and making more effective use of data already available at the metropolitan, regional, and national levels. The digital twin is recognized as a potential tool for research and decision support, capable of helping public administrations rethink urban planning, housing assets, and neighborhood development in response to demographic and social change. For the municipality, the digital twin should be developed to **encourage collaboration among different urban stakeholders throughout various stages of decision-making**. It should not only provide a broader range of data sources to support decisions, but also enable the transparent and responsive production of analyses, simulations, and forecasts.
- Finally, the feedback phase focuses on a key question: **which concrete actions could already benefit today from digital support**. Participants’ responses highlight very practical concerns, including household income and economic security, the integration of housing and welfare policies, combating loneliness and social isolation, accessibility for people with disabilities, road safety, the quality of public spaces, and equitable access to healthy food. This diversity of proposals confirms that the digital twin is not viewed as an end in itself, but rather as a tool that should serve urgent social priorities.

The meetings conclude with a shared understanding that the **digital twin will be a gradual process, built through experimentation and pilot projects** rather than serving as an

immediate solution. The main challenge that emerged clearly from the public discussion is ensuring **that digital technologies strengthen participation, social relationships, and the city's capacity to care for all its residents**, while keeping open the dialogue among citizens, civic organizations, and public institutions throughout the process leading to the official presentation of the work at the subsequent meeting at City Hall. **In this sense, the digital twin is understood as a social tool that supports relationships between communities and institutions**, rather than as a space where machines replace human beings. PianetaLab presents itself as a space for mediation between the scientific, social, and political spheres, with the goal of supporting the implementation of the Civic Digital Twin project by the authorities and institutions responsible for it.

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